

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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MUTATSION JARAYON

O‘roqbayeva O.A.

Mirzo Ulug‘bek nomidagi O‘zbekiston Milliy universiteti Jizzax filiali
E-mail: ozodaoroqboeva@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: O‘zgaruvchanlik deyilganda barcha tirik organizmlarning o‘zgarishi tushuniladi. Mutatsiyalar irsiy belgilarining o‘zgarishi natijasida yuz beradi va nasldan- naslga beriladi. Yangi belgi va xususiyatlar paydo bo‘ladi yoki bor belgi yo‘qolishi ham mumkin. Organizmlarning turli xillarda bo‘lishiga mutatsion o‘zgaruvchanlik natijasidir. Organizmlar o‘rtasidagi farq genotipining o‘zgarishi bilan bog‘liq. O‘zgaruvchanlik ikkiga bo‘linadi. Bular irsiy va irsiy bo‘lmagan o‘zgaruvchanlikka ajratiladi.

Kalit so‘zlar: mutatsiya, gen mutatsiyalari, xromosoma mutatsiyalari, genom mutatsiyalari, dominant.

Mutatsiya organizm u yoki bu belgilarning o‘zgarishiga olib keluvchi genetik materialning to‘satdan tabiiy yoki sun‘iy irsiy o‘zgarishi. Mutatsiya haqidagi ta‘limotga gollandiyalik botanik X.De Friz asos solgan (1901). Mutatsiyaning molekulyar mexanizmi XX asrlarning o‘rtalarida olib borilgan molekulyar genetika sohasidagi tadqiqotlar bilan bog‘liq. Mutatsiya hosil qilish virus va mikroorganizmlardan boshlab barcha yuksak o‘simliklar, hayvonlar va odam uchun xos bo‘lgan tiriklikning universal xossasidir. Gen mutatsiyalari. Gen mutatsiyasi molekular darajada ro‘y beradi. Gen mutatsiyasi ko‘p hollarda fenotipda yangi belgini rivojlantiradi. Gen mutatsiyalari nukleotidlarning soni ortishi, o‘rin almashinishi bilan kechadi. DNK dagi nuklotidlarning o‘rin almashinishi 2 xil bo‘ladi: Bir purin azotli asosining ikkinchi purin azotli asosi yoki bir pirimidin azotli asosining ikkinchi pirimidin azotli asosi bilan almashinishiga tranzitsiya deyiladi. Purin asosining pirimidin asosi bilan aksincha, pirimidin asosining purin bilan almashinishi transversiya deb nomlanadi. Har qanday aminokislota kodini mutatsiya tufayli terminator UAG kodiga o‘zgarishi polipeptid zanjiri sintezini ertaroq tugallanishiga olib keladi.

Geteroziota organizmda paydo bo‘lishiga qarab ikkiga bo‘linadi:

Dominant mutatsiyalar. Retsessiv mutatsiyalar.

Dominant mutatsiyalar polidaktliya (ortiqcha barmoqlilik), katarakta (ko‘z shoxpardasinini xiralashuvi), braxidaktliya (kalta barmoqlilik) kabilar misol bo‘ladi. Retsessiv mutatsiyalarga gemofiliya, daltonizm, tug‘ma karlik, albinizm kabilar misol bo‘ladi. Agar mutatsiya dominant bo‘lsa, birinchi avlodni o‘zidayoq yuzaga chiqadi. Retsessiv bo‘lsa ikkinchi yoki undan keyingi avlodlarda paydo bo‘lishi mumkin. Mutatsiyalarning kelib chiqish sabablariga ko‘ra: spontan va indutsirlangan mutatsiyalarga ajratiladi. Spontan mutatsiyalarni keltirib chiqaruvchi sabab aniq emas, ular o‘z- o‘zidan paydo bo‘ladigan mutatsiyalardir. Atrof- muhitda mutagen omillar ko‘p bo‘lsa, ular spontan mutatsiyalarni bir necha martaga oshirib

yuboradi. Indutsirlangan mutatsiyalar inson tomonidan ma'lum maqsadlarda hosil qilinadi. Bunday mutatsiyalarni keltirib chiqaruvchi mutagenlar 3 guruhga ajratiladi: fizik (radiktiv nurlar, rentgen nurlari, harorat); Kimyoviy (organik va anorganik moddalar); biologik (viruslar, toksinlar). Irsiyatga berilishiga qarab generativ va somatik mutatsiyalar farq qiladi. Generativ mutatsiyalar ya'ni jinsiy hujayralarda sodir bo'ladigan va nasldan naslga o'tadigan mutatsiyalardir. Tabiati bo'yicha generativ mutatsiyalarning somatik mutatsiyalardan farqi yo'q, chunki ikkalasi ham xromasomlar strukturasi o'zgarishi natijasida kuzatiladi.

Mutatsiyalar qayerda hosil bo'lishiga ko'ra bir necha guruhlarga bo'linadi: Xromasoma mutatsiyalari har bir biologik tur boshqa turdan xromasomalarning soni, shakli, hajmi bilan farqlanadi. Xromasoma strukturasi o'zgarishi bilan bog'liq mutatsiyalar xromasoma mutatsiyalari deb nomlanadi. Genom mutatsiyalari. Poliplodiya- xromasomlar gaploid to'plamining karrali ortishi. Olimlar o'simlik urug'lariga kolxitsin moddasi bilan ta'sir qilib ko'plab poliploid formalar oldilar. Kolxitsin moddasi bo'linish urug'ining hosil bo'lishini buzadi va oqibatda mitozning metafazasida xromasomlar ikki qutbga tarqalmay ona hujayra markazida qoladi. Modifikatsion o'zgaruvchanlik bir xil genotipga ega organizmlarda tashqi muhit omillari ta'sirida vujudga keladigan fenotipik tafovutlar modifikatsion o'zgaruvchanlik deb ataladi.

Xulosa: mutatsion jarayon bu genetik materialning tabiiy yoki suniy o'zgarishli bo'lib, urarning organizmlar evalyutsiyasida muxim ro'l o'ynaydi. Mutatsiyalar organizmlarning turli xil sharoitda o'zgarishida va yangi sharoitlarga moslashishiga imkon beradi.

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